

Market Failure in the EV Sector: The Case of Pakistan

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Pakistan's electric vehicle policy has faced limited success, mainly because of high taxes, not enough incentives, and a lack of proper charging infrastructure. Market failure is reflected in this situation, as the free market leads to the underconsumption of EVs. This is the case even though EVs have significant societal benefits, such as reduced pollution and lower carbon emissions. Positive externalities prevent the full capacity of the social benefits of EVs from being explored, discouraging widespread adoption. The article I have chosen has also discussed the issues of public goods, like charging infrastructure, which are underprovided due to them being non-excludable and non-rivalrous. This commentary explores how government intervention can fix these failures and improve efficiency and adoption of EVs through targeted government intervention.

EVs produce positive externalities because their usage reduces air pollution in

contrast to fossil fuel-powered cars. Positive externalities happen because their usage reduces air pollution. It improves public health and lowers reliance on fossil fuels. These benefits are, though, not fully captured in the market price of EVs. As a result, the private market produces and consumes less than the socially optimal quantity. This underconsumption is a market failure in effect. In Pakistan, high import prices and sales taxes on EVs have increased their retail prices, which discourages consumers. The article says that experts argue that EVs like hybrids and electric bikes should get tax incentives.

However, the lack of policy and high taxes discourages both consumers and manufacturers. The lack of charging stations is another form of market failure; these stations can be considered as quasi-public goods. When they are installed, they are non-rivalrous and often non-excludable. This leads to underprovision by private firms, as profit is not guaranteed without government support; the government has an important role to play to fix these failures. One solution is to subsidize the production and consumption of EVs, which shifts the MPB curve closer to the MSB curve. Another solution is to invest in public infrastructure like charging networks, which removes the barriers to adoption.

Market failure occurs when the allocation of goods and services by a free market is not efficient. In this case, two types of failures are evident, which are positive externalities, as EVs benefit individuals more than people realize. The second market failure identified is Public Goods Underprovision, as charging infrastructure is not profitable for the private sector alone. The market would remain stuck at Q_1 without government intervention, which is below the socially optimal level Q_2 . This misallocation of resources results in a welfare loss and a missed opportunity to address broader issues like climate change and urban pollution.

Market Failure: Underprovision of Charging Infrastructure in Pakistan

The government reduces taxes and improves policies; however, there are still some downsides. Government budget constraints can make it difficult for subsidies and infrastructure to be provided; there is a lack of public funding as well, which can cause a strain on the economy. Subsidies are only applied to expensive electric cars; the benefits may only be achieved for wealthy consumers. Equity can be improved by extending support to electric bikes and small EVs, which are more affordable for the average citizen.

Implementation risks, such as policy inconsistency, can involve shifting tax regimes and a lack of long-term commitment can discourage private investment. If EVs are imported, then the government and the market could face the negative impact of foreign subsidies, making them externally dependent. A solution is to link the incentives to local production and assembly. Government intervention overall is very important, but it must target equitability and sustainability to correct the market failure effectively.

Another critical consideration is the long-term economic and environmental gains of EV adoption, which outweigh the short-term fiscal costs. While subsidies and infrastructure investments need significant government spending, the reduction in healthcare costs because of lowered air pollution can improve Pakistan's trade

balance and public finances over time. Starting a local EV industry from the ground up could spark innovation, create new jobs, and increase productivity.

This gives the country a huge opportunity to compete in a constantly innovating, highly competitive industry. Policymakers need transparency in subsidy allocation to avoid corruption and prioritize renewable energy sources for charging stations to maximize environmental benefits. A slower implementation of this policy would be quite beneficial, as the technology would develop slowly over time as well.

The Pakistani EV market highlights how market failure due to positive externalities and underprovided public goods can lead to inefficient outcomes. The article portrays a real-life example of when government inaction and weak policy could result in socially beneficial goods being underconsumed. By applying microeconomic theory and evaluating the costs and benefits of intervention, effective policy becomes desirable and necessary for the country to be able to be successful in this industry and for the country to move forward with progressive innovations.